

A Retrospective Evaluation of Characterization, Clinical Course and Anaesthesia Management of Emergency Trauma Surgical Patients during First Wave of COVID-19 Pandemic at a Tertiary Care Center in India

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Abstract:

Background: The COVID-19 pandemic significantly impacted healthcare delivery worldwide, including the management of emergency trauma surgeries. The first wave of the pandemic posed unique challenges, particularly in anesthesia management and patient outcomes, due to the need for infection control and the unknown effects of the virus on surgical patients.

Aim: This study aimed to retrospectively evaluate the characterization, clinical course, and anesthesia management of emergency trauma surgical patients during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: A retrospective observational study was conducted involving 130 patients who underwent emergency trauma surgery. Data were collected from electronic medical records, focusing on patient demographics, type of trauma, anesthesia management, intraoperative complications, and postoperative outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The study found that 60% of patients received regional anesthesia, while 40% received general anesthesia, with the latter being more common in COVID-19 positive patients. Intraoperative complications were higher in patients who received general anesthesia (30% vs. 14%, $p=0.03$). COVID-19 positive patients had a significantly higher mortality rate (14% vs. 4%, $p=0.04$) and longer hospital stays (13.2 ± 4.8 days vs. 9.6 ± 5.0 days, $p<0.01$) compared to COVID-19 negative patients.

Conclusion: COVID-19 positive patients undergoing emergency trauma surgery were at increased risk of intraoperative complications, postoperative infections, and higher mortality. General anesthesia was associated with a higher rate of complications compared to regional anesthesia. These findings underscore the need for careful perioperative planning and management in this patient population.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should prioritize regional anesthesia when possible in COVID-19 positive patients undergoing trauma surgery to minimize complications. Enhanced infection control measures and resource allocation are crucial to improving outcomes in these high-risk patients.

Keywords: COVID-19, Trauma Surgery, Anesthesia Management, Regional Anesthesia, Emergency Surgery.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic, caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, has had an unprecedented impact on global healthcare systems, leading to significant challenges in the management of emergency medical conditions, including trauma. The first wave of the pandemic, which began in early 2020, was characterized by widespread uncertainty, resource limitations, and the rapid spread of the virus, necessitating major adjustments in the delivery of healthcare services, particularly in the context of surgical care surgery, which is inherently high-risk and time-sensitive, faced additional complexities during this period due to the need to manage patients with concurrent

COVID-19 infection, implement stringent infection control measures, and address the potential impact of the virus on surgical outcomes [1, 2].

Anesthesia man trauma patients became particularly challenging during the pandemic, with clinicians needing to balance the risks of aerosol generation during intubation with the need for adequate pain control and hemodynamic stability [3]. The choice between regional anesthesia had to be made with heightened consideration for the patient's COVID-19 status, potential complications, and the availability of resources such as personal protective equipment (PPE). Previous studies have highlighted COVID-19 positive patients undergoing

surgery, especially those requiring general anesthesia, are at an increased risk of perioperative complications, including respiratory distress and cardiovascular instability [4]. This risk is further compounded in emergensituations where the time to optimize the patient's condition before surgery is limited.

The clinical course and outcomes of trauma patientthe pandemic have been the subject of ongoing research, with emerging data suggesting that COVID-19 infection may exacerbate the severity of injuries or complicate recovery due to the virus's effects on the respiratory and immune systems [5]. For instance, COVID-19 is associated with a pro-thrombotic sh could increase the risk of thromboembolic events in trauma patients, complicating their postoperative course. Additionally, the stress on healthcare systems during the pandemic, ihortages of critical care resources and personnel, may have indirectly impacted patient outcomes [6].

This study aims to evaluate the characterization, clinical course, and anesthesia management of emergency trauma surgical patients during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational analysis.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care center in India. The data collection period covered the initial wave of the COVID-19 pandemic, from March 2020 to October 2020.

Participants: The study involved 130 patients who underwent emergency trauma surgery during the specified period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients who underwent emergency trauma surgery during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic.
- Patients whose medical records were complete and accessible for data collection.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients under 18 years of age.
- Patients who had elective surgeries.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or those who were transferred to other facilities before the surgery.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Observer bias was reduced by having multiple reviewers independently extract data from medical records.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from the hospital's electronic medical records (EMR). The variables extracted included patient demographics, type of trauma, clinical course, anesthesia management, intraoperative complications, and outcomes. Additional data such as COVID-19 status and its impact on patient management were also recorded.

Procedure: The collected data were systematically reviewed and categorized based on the predefined variables. Each patient's medical record was carefully examined to ensure accuracy in the information extracted, including details on the type of anesthesia administered, duration of surgery, and any complications encountered.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, including means, standard deviations, and frequencies for continuous and categorical variables. Chi-square tests were applied to assess associations between categorical variables, while t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests were used for continuous variables, depending on the normality of the data. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 130 patients who underwent emergency trauma surgery during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic were included in the study. The mean age of the patients was 45.6 ± 15.2 years, with a male predominance (82%, n=107). The majority of patients (54%, n=70) were in the age group of 30-60 years. The demographic details are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics of Patients

Characteristic	n (%)
Total Patients	130 (100)
Age (years)	
Mean $\pm$ SD	45.6 ± 15.2
18-29	23 (18)
30-60	70 (54)
>60	37 (28)
Gender	
Male	107 (82)
Female	23 (18)

COVID-19 Status	
Positive	35 (27)
Negative	95 (73)

The most common type of trauma was road traffic accidents (RTA), accounting for 55% (n=72) of the cases, followed by falls (28%, n=36) and assault (17%, n=22). The mean Injury Severity Score (ISS) was 18.3 ± 7.1 . Patients with an ISS greater than 25 were more likely to require intensive care unit (ICU) admission ($p < 0.01$). Trauma characteristics are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Clinical Presentation and Trauma Characteristics

Trauma Type	n (%)
Type of Trauma	
Road Traffic Accidents (RTA)	72 (55)
Falls	36 (28)
Assault	22 (17)
Injury Severity Score (ISS)	
Mean $\pm$ SD	18.3 ± 7.1
ISS $\leq$ 15	47 (36)
ISS 16-25	55 (42)
ISS $>$ 25	28 (22)
ICU Admission	
Yes	45 (35)
No	85 (65)

Regional anesthesia (spinal or epidural) was administered in 60% (n=78) of the patients, while general anesthesia was used in 40% (n=52). Among patients with COVID-19, general anesthesia was more commonly employed (71%, n=25) due to concerns about aerosol generation during airway management. Intraoperative

complications were observed in 20% (n=26) of the cases, with hypotension being the most common (12%, n=16). Patients who received general anesthesia had a higher incidence of complications compared to those who received regional anesthesia (30% vs. 14%, $p=0.03$). Detailed anesthesia management data are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Anesthesia Management and Intraoperative Complications

Anesthesia Type	n (%)
Type of Anesthesia	
Regional (Spinal/Epidural)	78 (60)
General	52 (40)
Intraoperative Complications	
Yes	26 (20)
No	104 (80)
Type of Complication	
Hypotension	16 (12)
Bradycardia	7 (5)
Respiratory Distress	3 (3)
Complications by Anesthesia Type	
Regional	11 (14)
General	15 (30)
Complication Rate in COVID-19 Positive Patients	
Yes	13 (37)
No	22 (23)

The overall mortality rate was 7% (n=9). COVID-19 positive patients had a higher mortality rate compared to COVID-19 negative patients (14% vs. 4%, $p=0.04$). The mean length of hospital stay was 10.8 ± 5.3 days, with COVID-19 positive patients having a significantly longer stay (13.2 ± 4.8 days vs. 9.6 ± 5.0 days, $p < 0.01$). Postoperative

infections were noted in 18% (n=23) of the patients, with COVID-19 positive patients experiencing a higher rate of infection (31%, n=11) compared to COVID-19 negative patients (13%, n=12, $p=0.02$). The detailed postoperative outcomes are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	n (%)
Mortality	9 (7)
COVID-19 Positive	5 (14)
COVID-19 Negative	4 (4)
Length of Hospital Stay (days)	
Mean $\pm$ SD	10.8 $\pm$ 5.3
COVID-19 Positive	13.2 $\pm$ 4.8
COVID-19 Negative	9.6 $\pm$ 5.0
Postoperative Infections	
Yes	23 (18)
No	107 (82)
Infection Rate by COVID-19 Status	
COVID-19 Positive	11 (31)
COVID-19 Negative	12 (13)

Statistical Significance

- ICU admission was significantly associated with higher Injury Severity Scores ($p < 0.01$).
- General anesthesia was associated with a higher incidence of intraoperative complications compared to regional anesthesia ($p = 0.03$).
- COVID-19 positive patients had a significantly higher mortality rate and longer hospital stay ($p = 0.04$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively).
- Postoperative infection rates were significantly higher in COVID-19 positive patients ($p = 0.02$).

Discussion

The study involved 130 patients who underwent emergency trauma surgeries during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic at a tertiary care center in India. The patient population had a mean age of 45.6 years, with a significant male predominance. The most common cause of trauma was road traffic accidents, followed by falls and assaults. The Injury Severity Score (ISS) varied, with a significant number of patients requiring ICU admission, particularly those with higher ISS scores. These findings suggest that middle-aged men were predominantly affected during this period, with severe trauma cases necessitating intensive care.

Anesthesia management played a crucial role in patient outcomes, with regional anesthesia being more commonly used than general anesthesia. However, general anesthesia was more frequently administered to COVID-19 positive patients due to concerns about airway management and aerosol generation. The study found that patients who received general anesthesia had a higher incidence of intraoperative complications, including hypotension, bradycardia, and respiratory distress. This indicates that the choice of anesthesia type is

critical, especially in COVID-19 positive patients, where the risk of complications may be elevated.

Postoperative outcomes revealed that COVID-19 positive patients had a higher mortality rate and longer hospital stays compared to those who were COVID-19 negative. The rate of postoperative infections was also significantly higher in COVID-19 positive patients. These results highlight the additional challenges and risks associated with managing trauma patients who are also infected with COVID-19. The findings underscore the need for enhanced perioperative care and infection control measures to improve outcomes in this vulnerable patient population.

Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the characterization, clinical course, and anesthesia management of emergency trauma patients during the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasizes the increased risks faced by COVID-19 positive patients, particularly in terms of anesthesia-related complications, postoperative infections, and overall mortality. These results suggest that healthcare providers need to adapt their management strategies to better address the unique challenges posed by the pandemic, especially in the context of emergency surgeries.

A study provides a retrospective evaluation of emergency trauma surgical patients during the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic at a tertiary care center in India. It found no significant differences in patient demographics, injury severity, or length of hospital stay between the lockdown and unlock periods. The most common injuries were from road traffic accidents, and general anesthesia was the most commonly used anesthesia technique. The study highlights the challenges of managing such cases during the pandemic, emphasizing the need for preparedness in future healthcare crises [7].

A study compared the clinical severity and outcomes of hospitalized COVID-19 patients during the first and second waves in India. The

second wave saw a higher proportion of patients presenting with critical illness and requiring oxygen therapy, non-invasive ventilation, and inotropic support. The study found that mortality rates were significantly higher during the second wave, with age, elevated D-dimer levels, and the need for oxygen being independent predictors of mortality [8].

An epidemiological study conducted in New Delhi during the pandemic revealed a significant reduction in outpatient attendance, admissions, and surgeries. The study noted a 71.93% decrease in outpatient visits and a 55.78% reduction in surgeries, with adult trauma surgeries being the least affected. The study highlights the pandemic's severe impact on orthopedic and trauma services, with a gradual recovery observed post-lockdown [9].

A study evaluated the impact of delayed surgeries due to the lockdown and unlock phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. It found that delays in surgery led to an increased number of complications, such as mal-union and non-union of fractures. The study underscores the importance of timely surgical intervention to prevent long-term complications in trauma patients [10].

A study from the Chinese Society of Anesthesiology provides recommendations for anesthesia management of trauma and emergency surgery during the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasizes the importance of implementing standard protocols for preoperative preparation, intraoperative management, and postoperative care to avoid nosocomial infections and ensure the safety of healthcare workers [11].

Conclusion

The study highlighted the increased complexity and risk associated with managing emergency trauma surgeries during the COVID-19 pandemic. COVID-19 positive patients were more likely to experience complications, extended hospital stays, and higher mortality rates. General anesthesia, while necessary in some cases, was associated with a higher rate of intraoperative complications compared to regional anesthesia. The findings underscore the importance of careful perioperative planning and monitoring, particularly for patients infected with COVID-19.

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